

41°0'0"W 40°0'0"W 39°0'0"W

18°0'0"S
19°0'0"S
20°0'0"S
21°0'0"S

Corymbia citriodora

E. urophylla x E. grandis

Eucalyptus grandis

Eucalyptus urophylla

N

0 75 150 km

Geographic Coordinate Systems

Datum: WGS 84